

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF NARCISSISTIC-SELF

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The article analyzes the concept of "Narcissistic-Self" as a characteristic of the Self-image of Self-concept's structure. The results of standardization of the method of psychodiagnostics of Narcissistic-Self of personality are shown, which contains the scale: "Insignificant-Self", "Grandiose-Self", Striving for the perfect Self-object, "Demonstrative-Self", "Narcissistic aggression", "Absorbance in fantasy", "Expectation of a special attitude", "Envious-Self". The correlation relations between Narcissistic-Self and the hubristic motivation of personality are determined.

Key words: narcissistic Self, Self-concept, Self-image, hubristic motivation, desire for superiority, desire for perfection.

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Психодіагностика Нарцисичного-Я

У статті проаналізовано поняття «нарцисичне Я» як характеристика образу Я у структурі Я-концепції. Подано результати стандартизації методики психодіагностики нарцисичного Я особистості, яка містить шкали: «Я-нікчемне», «Я-грандіозне», Прагнення до ідеального Self-об'єкту, «Я-демонстративне», Нарцисична агресія, Поглиненість у фантазії, Очікування особливого ставлення, «Я-заздрісне». Визначено кореляційні зв'язки між нарцисичним Я та губристичною мотивацією особистості.

Ключові слова: нарцисичне Я, Я-концепція, образ Я, губристична мотивація, прагнення до переваги, прагнення до досконалості.

Introduction. Narcissism acts as an attribute of self-consciousness of a person who strives for self-affirmation. Within the psychological norm, narcissism manifests itself in the specific configuration of narcissistic rice, causes an ambivalence of self-esteem in the continuum, "I am Null - I am grandiose" the polarization of self-consciousness within the limits of "Relations with others" and "Searching for yourself". The closest approach to determine the place of narcissism in the structure of self-consciousness is the body-oriented approach, focused on the definition of the essence of bodily Self. Narcissism is associated with the support of self-esteem by

means of confirmation from others, characterized by a disproportionate degree of concern exclusively by oneself, and not so much the hidden aspects of its identity and integrity as its own external merits, prestige, and "image". Narcissism can be defined as the cognitive-affective enthusiasm of the individual by him- or herself, or as a concentration of psychological interest in Self (Fomenko, 2013, 2014, 2018).

Specific narcissistic personality is an extremely "bloated" representation of oneself, a grandiose sense of self-importance, a reappraisal of the abilities and knowledge, which leads to boasting, snobbishness, neglect and pride. Feeling a huge need for enthusiasm and approval, a person with a high degree of narcissism easily takes overestimated evaluations of his or her actions, and when stopping the external fertilization of self-esteem by the enthusiasm of others, he or she feels anxiety and boredom. O. Kernberg (2006) showed that the self-consciousness of the narcissistic person is split, "isocipated" and has a two-level "organization: on the surface level, it is defiantly idealized, pathologically grandiose, whereas at the deep level there is a "crippled" Real Self.

According to S. Sokolov (2009), narcissism is an universal and necessary component of a healthy self-consciousness. The functions of narcissism are aimed at protecting, filling and preserving structural integrity, temporal stability and positive-affective coloring of the person's perception of oneself.

Excessive personal narcissism (Cooper, 1986) negatively affects the quality of human life, its relations with others and activity. Thus, narcissistic individuals are painfully and sometimes aggressively responsive to criticism due to problems in the field of self-perception and autoaggression, which, in turn, affects relationships with others. In addition, narcissistic individuals are hard hit by age crises and changes associated with existential aspects of life, as well as experiencing serious difficulties in interpersonal relationships. Thus, narcissism causes the formation of some components of the Self-concept. The activities of individuals with excessive narcissism are characterized by difficulties in the creative process, the goal settings and achieving results (Beck, 2002). Narcissistic individuals also experience serious difficulties in relationship (Johnson, 1987). A. Dmitrieva (2010) proves that narcissistic individuals are characterized by a sub-optimal level of self-esteem.

The problem of narcissistic features of a healthy person goes up in the study of K. Shamshikova (2010), which, according to narcissistic manifestations of personality, within the limits of the psychological norm, understands the totality of narcissistic features (persistent, repeatable in

various situations, the peculiarities of behavior: the grandiose sense of self-importance, the absorption in the fantasy of unlimited success, beliefs in own uniqueness, need for capture, manipulation in interpersonal relations, feeling of privilege, lack of empathy, jealousy to achievements of others, arrogant behavior). According to the author, healthy narcissism can be represented as a universal and necessary component of consciousness. Narcissism exists as a continuum of transitional forms, defines the orientation of the individual and acts as an unconscious part of the system of personality representations of oneself.

Analyzing the meaningful characteristics of the Self-concept and Self-Image, along with their classification by sphere ("Social-Self", "Active-Self", "Physical- or Bodily-Self", etc.) or character ("I am positive", "I'm negative") one's manifestation, it is expedient to concretize the awareness of the subject of his or her own personality traits, behavioral manifestations, attitudes and beliefs associated with his attitude towards self-improvement and the achievement of the Ideal-Self, which indicate the ambivalence of self-esteem in the continuum "I am-worthless-I am-grandiose", the polarization of self-consciousness in the limit of "relations with others" and "self-search", which turns out to be possible through the introduction of the concept of "Narcissistic-Self." The high degree of development of "Narcissistic-Self" within the Self-image indicates the concern of the subject of his appearance, image, appearance in the eyes of others, awareness of one's own tendencies to self-admiration, self-satisfaction, self-affirmation, as well as fear to be in a position that gives another unconditional superiority over the subject.

Research methods and sample. The creation of psychodiagnostic methods of narcissism included the translation of 163 original statements of the narcissism assessment methodology (clinical and psychological test method, developed by F.-W.Deneke and B. Hilgenstock and adapted in 2003) and 67 statements of the questionnaire "Narcissistic features of personality" O.A. Shamshikova, N.M. Klepikova (2010). 50 of these statements were selected that correspond to the peculiarities of manifestations of Narcissistic Self.

The psychometric sample was 438 people (248 women and 190 men, in particular: adolescents (14-16 years) - 123, students - 189, 126 adults. The average age of respondents was 24,6 years.

Results. The reliability of 50 points, the questionnaire revealed the statistics of the alpha Kronbach, was 0,954. Items 8 and 41 worsen the reliability indicators, so they were removed from the final version of the questionnaire. After eliminating these items, the alpha was 0,961.

Factorization of data for 48 points formed 6 factors, which explain 89% dispersion. The first factor (30.1% dispersion, factor weight is 14,46) was created by 15 items (23, 21, 4, 26, 16, 31, 14, 33, 11, 1, 3, 13, 17, 24 , 29), for instance: 23d "Usually I like to look good and get compliments in this regard" (0,9578), 21st "I have a better mood when somebody praises me" (0,9563), 26th "It's sometimes unbearable to notice my own insignificance " (0,9551), 16 "It would be great be praised for every step you make" (0,9535), 31st "I like somebody's caring for me" (0,9527), Consequently, the factor is formed by the points of such original scales as "I am demonstrative" (56% of the content of the factor) and "*Aspiration to the ideal Self-object*" (31% of the content of the factor).

The second factor (21,4% of the dispersion, factor weight is 10,27) contains 13 items: 15th "I think that communicating with me is a real pleasure for people" (0,9288), 9th "I usually want to communicate with talented and successful people" (0,9113), 38th "It seems to me that other people underestimate my real abilities" (0,9097), 39th "Sometimes I feel insecure about attractive people" (0,8039). The content of the second factor was the points of the scales of beliefs in one's uniqueness and grandiose sense of self-importance (53,8% of the factor content). In addition, the factor absorbed all points of the expectations of a special attitude and the sense of envy.

The third factor (15,6% dispersion, factor weight is 7,48) contains paragraphs 34th "Often, I feel uncertain, because I can not know too much" (0,9423), 27th "It's sometimes unbearable to notice myself as nevertheless insignificant person"(0,9350), 35th "I sometimes feel unbearably great in my sense of powerlessness" (0,9326), 28th "Sometimes I feel like nothing" (0,9322), 43d "Attractive people causing insecurity in me" (0,8959), 49 "If something fails, I am inclined (at once) to doubt my abilities and talents immediately" (0,8958), 19th "Sometimes I seem to myself useless " (0,8551), 7th "Sometimes I seem an ugly and unbearable person" (0,8394). The factor is formed by points of powerless and insignificant Self scales.

The fourth factor (12,2% of the dispersion, factor weight is 5,87) is created by paragraphs 46th "If someone disgraces me with others, I think: "I'll give you some thanks for that!" (0,8519), 50th "If some sort of thing fails, I am ready to shake myself out of fury" (0,88512), 42d "I will internally throw the whole (if I do not get the recognition I deserved " (0,8503), 30th "It may be very wrong for me if I do not get what I really want" (0,88470), 25th "I often caught myself thinking of revenge if someone had humiliated me" (0,8378), 18th "I can be scared to be angry if I'm wrong" (0,7760), 20th "I am really angry when I try to impose tasks that are

consciously below my level" (0,7634). The factor was created by points of the scale of "narcissistic rage".

The fifth factor (7,6% of the dispersion, factor weight is 3.69), formed by 4 items (22, 32, 12, 10), for instance: 12th "Sometimes I see myself as a prominent person in my fantasies" (0,9119), 10th "I think that one day, glory and recognition will come to me" (0,8601). The factor is filled with points of the scale of absorption in fantasy.

The sixth factor (4.6% dispersion, factor weight is 2,23) is formed by items 37th "Sometimes I am annoyed by slow service and queues in public places" (0,6375), 47th "Sometimes I'm annoyed if someone is late" (0, 6321), 5th "Sometimes I feel irritated because of the insignificant requirements imposed on me" (0,6257). The factor was created by the points of expectation of a special attitude.

Consequently, the content of the psychodiagnostic method of narcissism of the person is represented by the following scales:

1. "Insignificant-Self " containing 8 points of the Weak Self Scales and the Weak Self (the scale of F.-W.Deneke and B.Hilgenstock questionnaire ()) and characterizes the awareness of the personality of his own helplessness, low social performance, the propensity to globalization and maximize the negative assessment your surroundings. High scores on the scale suggest a high self-esteem of the feeling of inner emptiness, subjective perception of fragility and insignificance of personality, loneliness as a manifestation of the fear of social failure. High indicators for this parameter also indicate intense depressive experiences of senselessness, pointless life, inferiority, cowardice, inner emptiness, impotence, hopelessness, from which the person cannot defend himself, destructive motives with the treatment of aggression against himself. Violation of the regulation of a sense of self-worth accompanies the dominant experience of shame and the fear of inferiority's disclosure by others.

2. "Grandiose-Self", containing 7 points of scales of grandiose sense of self-worth and belief in the uniqueness (O.A. Shamshikova, N.M. Klepikova). High scores on this scale indicate the existence of fantastic fantasies about their giftedness, uniqueness, attractiveness, talent, the benefits and superiority of others, illusory ideas about the possibility of achieving absolutely any purpose, the denial of the existence of any limits of their abilities, social efficiency, attractiveness, the absoluteization of their leadership qualities as a hypercompensating need for power.

The first two scales characterize two polar personality trends that function together, forming a pattern of narcissistic personality traits.

3. Striving for the perfect Self-object contains all 6 points of the original scale, as well as item 1 "I would like to get acquainted with a

prominent or famous person", which in the original version refers to the scale of absorption in imagination, although the content corresponds to the orientation search for an ideal. The content of the scale involves dependence on others, while allowing the opportunity to take advantage of their help, to enjoy the contact with them, without fear of mesmerizing by their charm. Raising the indicators for this parameter reflects a decrease in satisfaction with the simultaneous search for an external idealized object, which in imaginations seems radiating the force. Identification with it stimulates a weak person, thus compensating for his own narcissistic deficit.

4. The "Demonstrative-Self" scale is created with 5 points of the original scale of need for constant attention and admiration and 4 points of the scale of praise and confirmation. High scores on this scale indicate the dependence on the attention of others, from confirmation of acceptance by others, their approval and admiration. Concern for their own appearance, the need to be in the center of attention, to receive compliments, to be the object of respect and the capture of others also characterizes high scores on this scale.

5. "Narcissistic aggression" corresponds to 7 points of the scale of narcissistic rage in F.-W.Deneke's & B.Hilgenstock's questionnaire and is characterized by destructive aggression, caused by the vulnerability of self-esteem, an exacerbated sense of self-importance in situations that threaten Ego.

6. "Absorbance in fantasy" scale corresponds to 4 points of the same name scale in O.A. Shamshikova's & N.M. Klepikova's version and describes fantasy aspirations for fame, recognition, triumph, approval by outstanding or authoritative people, public self-love.

7. "Expectation of a special attitude" (3 points on the same scale O.A. Shamshikova, N.M. Klepikova) characterizes a high degree of anxiety as a result of external factors, which endangers Narcissistic-Self. High scores on a scale are characterized by irritability, anxiety, instability in situations of illusory loss of control over others.

8. "Envious-Self" (3 points on the same scale as O.A. Shamshikova, N.M. Klepikova). The scale characterizes a tendency to envy people who are at risk of being narcissistic, especially to the more affluent and rich.

Convergent validity. A series of links between indicators of desire for perfection and narcissism has been determined, namely: negative correlations with "Insignificant-Self" ($r=-0,20$, $p<0,0001$) and Absorbance in fantasy ($r=-0,16$, $p<0,01$), a positive correlation with the Demonstrative-Self ($r=0,15$, $p<0,01$). The desire for superiority is more closely related to the indicators of narcissism: with the indicators of "Grandiose-Self" ($r=0,33$, $p<0,0001$), Demonstrative-Self ($r=0,32$, $p<0,0001$), Expecting a

special attitude ($r=0,40$, $p<0,0001$), Absorbance in fantasy ($r=0,36$, $p<0,0001$), “Envious-Self” ($r=0,28$, $p<0,0001$).

Table 1 shows the psychometric parameters of the Narcissistic-Self questionnaire, taking into account the normative values for each scale. Testing the test-retest reliability as a result of repeated testing of one sample ($n = 60$) in 2 months showed a high value for all indicators in 8 scales ($r_1 = 0,765$, $r_2 = 0,733$, $r_3 = 0,766$, $r_4 = 0,735$, $r_5 = 0,665$, $r_6 = 0,861$, $r_7 = 0,681$, $r_8 = 0,667$).

Table 1

Descriptive statistics of scales of the Narcissistic-Self questionnaire

Indicators	Mean	Min	Max	Std. dev	Average
“Insignificant-Self”	21,571	8,000	40,000	6,880	14-28
“Grandiose-Self”	21,977	7,000	35,000	8,105	14-28
Striving for the perfect Self-object	22,607	7,000	35,000	8,893	14-28
“Demonstrative-Self”	30,813	10,000	45,000	10,578	20-32
Narcissistic aggression	18,452	6,000	30,000	6,288	12-24
Absorbance in fantasy	14,594	4,000	20,000	3,218	10-18
Expecting a special attitude	8,858	3,000	15,000	3,445	5-12
“Envious-Self”	8,562	3,000	15,000	3,285	5-12

Discussion. Thus, the high degree of development of the desire for perfection is characterized by the high significance and power of Self, the freedom from fantasies in relation to his own outstanding future, the need for constant attention, admiration, approval, and self-affirmation through endorsement. In addition, the negative connection of the desire for perfection with the indicators of the Insignificant-Self indicates that declaring complete indifference to the assessment of those surrounding their social success is a protective narcissistic mechanism for subjects who strive for perfection, based on fear of being rejected. The denial of the possibility of failure and the complete neglect of the reactions of others in their behavior is a narcissistic manifestation of a person who strives for perfection.

Consequently, the desire for superiority is associated with a sense of one’s own grandeur, which implies the presence of ideas about the

exceptional talent and uniqueness. The desire for superiority is related to the extent of the development of illusory ideas about the possibility of achieving absolutely any purpose, the negation of the existence of any limits of abilities, social efficiency, attractiveness, the absolutization of the leadership qualities as a hypercompensating need for power.

Indicators of Demonstrative-Self are related to the desire for superiority. Consequently, the dependence on the attention of others, from the confirmation of acceptance by others, the approval and admiration is inherent in subjects, for whom the motivational force has the ability to be better than others. Concern for their own appearance, the need to be at the center of attention, to receive compliments, to be the object of respect and admiration of others also describes people with a desire for excellence and superiority.

High rates of absorption in fantasy are represented by the desire for fame, recognition, triumph, approval by prominent or authoritative people, inclusion in a special circle of communication, and public self-love also characterizes subjects with a strong desire for superiority.

Expectations of a special attitude as anxiety, irritability and inconsistency in situations of illusory loss of control over others are characteristic of a person with anxious desire for superiority.

Conclusions. According to concept of "Narcissistic Self" we created "Narcissistic Self Questionnaire". The results of the "Narcissistic Self Questionnaire" standardization have shown. Its validity and reliability were proved. Narcissistic Self correlates with hubristic motives – the desire for perfection and superiority.

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Appendix

Psychometric indicators of the questionnaire "Narcissistic Self"

Психометричні показники пунктів опитувальника «Нарцисичне Я»

Первинний номер	Кінцевий номер	Твердження	Альфа Кронбаха	Оригінальна шкала	Кінцева шкала
1	1	Мені б хотілося познайомитися з видатною або знаменитою людиною.	0,952	Поглиненість у фантазії	-
2	2	Думаю, що в мені є особливі задатки, тому люди з винятковими здібностями прагнуть мені допомогти.	0,954	Віра у власну унікальність.	Я-Грандіозне
3	3	У мене відразу підвищується настрій, коли поруч зі мною людина, якою я	0,952	Прагнення до ідеального Self-об'єкту	-

		захоплююся.			
4	4	Мені здається, що я уважно ставлюся до своєї зовнішності	0,952	Потреба в постійній увазі і захопленні	Я-демонстративне
5	5	Іноді я відчуваю роздратування через несуттєві вимоги, що пред'являються до мене.	0,954	Очікування особливого ставлення	-
6	6	Часом я відчуваю дискомфорт, перебуваючи серед тих, хто багатший мене.	0,954	Надмірна зайнятість почуттям заздрості	Я-заздрісне
7	7	Я іноді здаюсь собі бридким та нестерпним	0,954	Безсильне Self	Я-нікчемне
8	-	Я легко порушую правила дорожнього руху, якщо це не небезпечно для життя.	0,957	Зухвала, зарозуміла поведінка	видалений пункт
9	8	Зазвичай я прагну спілкуватися з талановитими і успішними людьми.	0,954	Грандіозне почуття самозначущості	Я-Грандіозне
10	9	Думаю, що одного разу до мене прийдуть і слава, і визнання.	0,954	Поглиненість у фантазії	-
11	10	Бувають моменти, коли мені подобається ловити на собі захоплені погляди.	0,952	Потреба в постійній увазі і захопленні	Я-демонстративне
12	11	Іноді в фантазіях я бачу себе видатною особистістю	0,954	Поглиненість у фантазії	-
13	12	Я часто тягнуся до людини, яка могла би окрилити мене своїми ідеями і планами.	0,952	Прагнення до ідеального Self-об'єкту	-
14	13	Мені сподобалося б як-небудь по-справжньому виявитися в центрі уваги.	0,952	Жага похвал і підтвердження	Я-демонстративне
15	14	Думаю, що спілкування зі мною людям доставляє шире задоволення.	0,954	Віра у власну унікальність	Я-Грандіозне
16	15	Було б чудово, якби тебе (як дитину) хвалили за кожен крок,	0,952	Жага похвал і підтвердження	Я-демонстративне

		який ти робиш.			
17	16	Іноді мені дуже хочеться отримати допомогу людини, яка може все, чого я не можу.	0,952	Прагнення до ідеального Self-об'єкту	-
18	17	Я можу страшно розлютитися, якщо мене несправедливо критикують	0,955	Нарцисична лють	Нарцисична агресія
19	18	Іноді я здаюся собі марним (марною) і непотрібним (непотрібною).	0,954	Безсильне Self	Я-нікчемне
20	19	Мене викликає справжню лють, коли мені намагаються нав'язати завдання, які свідомо нижче мого рівня.	0,955	Нарцисична лють	Нарцисична агресія
21	20	У мене поліпшується настрій, коли оточуючі мене хвалять.	0,952	Потреба в постійній увазі і захопленні	Я-демонстративне
22	21	Думаю, що з мене б вийшов хороший телеведучий	0,954	Поглиненість у фантазії	-
23	22	Зазвичай я люблю добре виглядати і отримувати у зв'язку з цим компліменти.	0,952	Потреба в постійній увазі і захопленні	Я-демонстративне
24	23	Я б охоче подружився (подружилася) з будь-яким значною особою.	0,951	Прагнення до ідеального Self-об'єкту	-
25	24	Я часто ловив (ла) себе на тому, що думаю про помсту, якщо мене хтось принизив.	0,955	Нарцисична лють	Нарцисична агресія
26	25	Моя самооцінка сильно підвищується, коли я відчуваю, що дуже подобаюся іншим.	0,952	Жага похвал і підтвердження	Я-демонстративне
27	26	Іноді нестерпно помічати, який(а) же я все-таки незначний(а).	0,954	Незначне Self	Я-нікчемне
28	27	Іноді я відчуваю себе нікчемною.	0,954	Безсильне Self	Я-нікчемне
29	28	Мені подобаються люди, які можуть захопити інших за	0,952	Прагнення до ідеального Self-об'єкту	-

		собою.			
30	29	Мені може стати дуже не по собі, якщо я не отримую те, що дуже хочу мати.	0,954	Нарцисична лють	Нарцисична агресія
31	30	Мені подобається, коли за мною доглядають	0,952	Жага похвал і підтвердження	Я-демонстративне
32	31	Було б непогано, якщо моя фотографія прикрасить обкладинку модного журналу.	0,954	Поглиненість у фантазії	-
33	32	Мені подобається відрізнятись від інших, модно одягатися.	0,952	Потреба в постійній увазі і захопленні	Я-демонстративне
34	33	Часто я відчуваю себе невпевнено, оскільки просто занадто мало можу і знаю	0,954	Незначне Self	Я-нікчемне
35	34	Почуття власного безсилля у мене іноді нестерпно велике	0,954	Безсилльне Self	Я-нікчемне
36	35	Мене просто тягне до людей, у яких є щось особливе	0,952	Прагнення до ідеального Self-об'єкту	-
37	36	Часом мене дратує повільне обслуговування та черги в громадських місцях	0,954	Очікування особливого ставлення	-
38	37	Часом мені здається, що інші люди недооцінюють мої реальні здібності	0,954	Віра у власну унікальність	Я-Грандіозне
39	38	Часом я відчуваю себе невпевнено поряд з привабливими людьми	0,954	Надмірна зайнятість почуттям заздрості	Я-заздрісне
40	39	Думаю, що мені все-таки вдасться домогтись в житті великого успіху.	0,954	Грандіозне почуття самозначущості	Я-Грандіозне
41	-	Іноді я нехтую громадським нормами і правилами, якщо вони в чомусь обмежують мене	0,957	Зухвала, зарозуміла поведінка	видалений пункт
42	40	Я внутрішньо весь (вся) скипаю, якщо не отримую визнання,	0,954	Нарцисична лють	Нарцисична агресія

		якого я заслужив(ла).			
43	41	Привабливі люди викликають у мені невпевненість.	0,954	Незначне Self	Я-нікчемне
44	42	Думаю, що люди, які погано до мене ставляться, просто не знають, який(а) я насправді.	0,954	Віра у власну унікальність	Я-Грандіозне
45	43	Іноді мені хочеться мати річ, яка є у іншого.	0,954	Надмірна зайнятість почуттям заздрості	Я-заздрісне
46	44	Якщо мене хтось ганьбить перед іншими, я думаю: "я тобі за це віддячу коли-небудь!"	0,954	Нарцисична лють	Нарцисична агресія
47	45	Часом я дратуюся, якщо хтось запізнюється.	0,954	Очікування особливого ставлення	-
48	46	Вважаю, що в мені ще багато нерозкритих талантів.	0,954	Грандіозне почуття самозначущості	Я-Грандіозне
49	47	Якщо мені щось не вдається, я схильний (схильна) відразу засумніватися в своїх здібностях і талантах.	0,954	Незначне Self	Я-нікчемне
50	48	Якщо якась справа не вдається, я готовий(а) просто луснути від люті.	0,954	Нарцисична лють	Нарцисична агресія

Оригінальний рукопис отримано 10 травня 2018 року

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